

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.3954 Max: 63.7863	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1214 *Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic <input type="checkbox"/>	Rabbit Project	
				In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 746-748
DEFINITION whitish layer abutting 1169				Covered by *SU: 1016	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS 1208 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay 30% silt 60% sand 10% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails IRON <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles RO <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae M <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster R <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range) F small bits		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal R <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)			
				Compaction		Color	
				<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original	
Northern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Western Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Eastern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
cut partially by 1175 cut by 1209							
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):				
Is abutted by: 1169			Abuts: 1169				
Is covered by: 1016, 1208			Covers: 1222				
Is cut by: 1175, 1209			Cuts:				
Is filled by:			Fills:				
OBSERVATIONS excavated with pickaxes - distinction of S limit unclear between 1169 and 1214							
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: W end of excavated area of area B Shape: irregular edge on the N; otherwise linear							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): large rocks protruding from W edge surface; no visible slope							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): rubble distributed evenly throughout; ceramic and small bone fragments also evenly distributed							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): relatively consistent thickness							
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):				
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight							
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping							
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular							
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
Observations:							

OB rocks

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

- layer is post-abandonment accumulation

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *LMB*

Revised by *CHM*

PDFd by *JJM*

Entered by

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on